

Update on the status of COMET experiment

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Abstract

Neutrino oscillation experiments have demonstrated that lepton flavor is violated for neutral leptons. However, charged lepton flavor violation (cLFV) has never been observed. The COMET experiment [1] aims to search for cLFV via the coherent, neutrinoless conversion of a muon bound to a nucleus into an electron ($\mu^- + N(Z, A) \rightarrow e^- + N(Z, A)$). COMET targets a single-event sensitivity of 10^{-17} over two phases, representing a four-order-of-magnitude improvement over the current limit set by SINDRUM-II in 2006 [2]. The experiment will begin with a low-intensity beam at J-PARC in 2027. This talk provided an update on the status of the COMET beamline, magnets, detectors, and schedule.

1 Theoretical context

Within the minimal extensions to the Standard Model (SM), with massive Dirac neutrinos to account for their oscillations [3], the $\mu \rightarrow e\gamma$ process should be possible at loop level. Its branching ratio, $B(\mu \rightarrow e\gamma)$, shown in Eq. 1 is highly suppressed by the ratio between the masses of neutrinos (m_ν) and W boson (M_W). U_{ij} are the elements of the Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (PMNS) neutrino mixing matrix.

$$B(\mu \rightarrow e\gamma) = \frac{3\alpha}{32\pi} \left| \sum_{j=1}^3 U_{ej} U_{\mu j}^* \frac{m_{\nu j}^2}{M_W^2} \right|^2 \sim O(10^{-54}) \quad (1)$$

As such a branching ratio is not observable, any observation of cLFV cannot only be explained by neutrino oscillations and would unambiguously point toward physics beyond the SM (BSM).

A number of processes associated with muon-to-electron ($\mu - e$) flavor violation are predicted by BSM models and are therefore investigated. One such process involves the decay of a muon in a bound state with an atom. This muonic atom is formed when a negatively charged muon is stopped in matter and captured on an outer shell of the atom. The muon undergoes a series of energy level transitions until it reaches the 1s ground state. In accordance with the SM, the muon in the ground state can either decay in orbit (DIO, Eq. 2) or be captured by the nucleus (Eq. 3). Several BSM models also predict a coherent conversion of the muon to an electron, without production of neutrinos (Eq. 4).

$$\mu^- N(A, Z) \rightarrow e^- \nu_\mu \bar{\nu}_e N(A, Z) \quad (2)$$

$$\mu^- N(A, Z) \rightarrow \nu_\mu N(A, Z - 1) \quad (3)$$

$$\mu^- N(A, Z) \rightarrow e^- N(A, Z) \quad (4)$$

The signature of this BSM process is the emission of a single electron with a well defined energy in a time interval consistent with the lifetime of the muonic atom. The electron energy, $E_{\mu e}$, is given by Eq. 5:

$$E_{\mu e} = m_{\mu} - B_{\mu} - E_{recoil} \quad (5)$$

Here, m_{μ} is the muon mass, B_{μ} the binding energy of 1s-state muonic atom and E_{recoil} the nuclear recoil energy. The energy of the signal electron (e.g. for Aluminum $E_{\mu e} = 104.97$ MeV) is fixed and significantly exceeds the maximal energy of an electron produced by the standard decay of a free muon (~ 52.8 MeV). However, the tail of the energy spectrum of the DIO electron can reach values close to the mass of the muon. Therefore, DIO electrons are considered as background for measurements of $\mu - e$ neutrinoless conversion.

Figure 1: COMET Phase I Layout: A 8-GeV pulsed proton beam is focused on a graphite target placed within a solenoidal magnet (see the top-left figure). The magnetic field extracts low-momentum pions in the backward direction of the interaction point. Next, a transport solenoid transports these pions as they decay into muons. The produced muon beam is focused on an aluminum target. There, the low-momentum muons are stopped to form muonic atoms. If a muon-electron coherent conversion without neutrinos occurs, the signal electron will be detected by the cylindrical detector surrounding the target (see the top right figure). This detector is called the CyDet. The StrECAL detectors, designed for COMET Phase-II (bottom right figure), will replace the CyDet at some point during Phase-I to perform a beam measurement program.

2 COMET experiment

The COMET experiment [1], which searches for cLFV, is located in the hadron experimental facility at J-PARC, Japan. In its final stage, COMET aims to reach an experimental sensitivity of 10^{-17} for the branching fraction of $\mu - e$ neutrinoless coherent conversion—an improvement of four orders of magnitude over the current world limit set by SINDRUM-II in 2006 [2]. An inter-

mediate stage, COMET Phase-I, for which the layout is shown in Fig. 1, is planned to perform direct background and beam measurements in order to reduce experimental uncertainties. The detectors designed for COMET final stage, namely the StrECAL (presented in section 4), are planned to be used during Phase-I for the beam measurement program. Phase-I will also search for $\mu - e$ neutrinoless coherent conversion using the so called CyDet detector (also presented in section 4). This intermediate stage of the experiment is expected to reach a single event sensitivity of the order of 10^{-15} — improving by two orders of magnitude the current limit. The following sections focus on the status of COMET Phase-I.

The strategy to achieve such a high-precision measurement relies on using a pulsed proton beam and a muonic atom with a long lifetime, such that the measurement window is contained between proton pulses. This approach effectively reduces beam-induced background. While the expected conversion rate increases with atomic number, the lifetime of the muonic atom decreases [9]. Aluminum is a good compromise between conversion rate and muonic atom lifetime. The first commissioning of the COMET facility, known as COMET Phase- α , took place in 2023. A slowly extracted, 8 GeV pulsed proton beam with a power of 260 W was focused on a thin (1 mm) graphite target. This phase provided an opportunity for beam tuning and beam profile measurements. Several detectors were employed for these studies, including a Muon Beam Monitor [8], a Straw Tube Tracker [5], and a Range Counter [7]. The first measurement of the momentum spectrum of the COMET muon beam was successfully performed.

3 Beamline

Proton beam: The COMET beam is an 8 GeV proton beam. For COMET Phase-I, the beam power will be 3.2 kW, increasing to 56 kW for Phase-II. Proton bunches are slowly extracted from the J-PARC main ring. To create the pulsed beam structure, only four of the nine available buckets are filled. COMET bunch structure consists of four bunches, with a 1.17 ns spacing between bunches. The spacing between consecutive four-bunch groups is 1.76 ns. The fraction of residual protons between bunches defines the beam “extinction”. High beam extinction is essential, as protons arriving between bunches can generate background events during the measurement time window. An extinction measurement was conducted at the K1.8BR beamline of the J-PARC hadron experimental facility in 2021, yielding an extinction better than 10^{-10} [6].

Proton target and magnetic system: The proton beam is focused on a graphite target for Phase-I and a tungsten target for Phase-II. This target is placed in a 4.4 T magnetic field (Pion Capture Solenoid, PCS) to extract negatively charged pions produced in backward from the interaction point. Selecting backward-produced particles is crucial, as these tend to have much lower momentum than those produced in the forward direction and soft muons are required to form muonic atoms. These low-momentum pions are then transported through a 90° curved transport solenoid (Muon Transport Solenoid, MTS) with a 3 T field, where they decay into muons. The MTS was confirmed to operate successfully during Phase- α . A 0.04 T dipole field is also applied within the MTS and together with a beam collimator at the MTS exit ensures the selection of low momentum, negative muons. The Bridge Solenoid (BS) connects the MTS to the Detector Solenoid (DS), where the Al stopping target is located. The PCS was installed in November 2024 in the COMET Hall and connected to the MTS. The DS and the BS were also deployed and successfully connected to the MTS in November 2025.

Stopping target: Finally, the muons are stopped by an aluminum target located at DS center. The baseline design has 17 disks, each 200 μm thick and 10 cm radius. A germanium detector is positioned downstream of the target to measure the muonic X-rays that accompany the muon capture, providing an estimate of the number of stopped muons.

4 Detectors

CyDet: The main detector for Phase-I is the cylindrical detector (CyDet), which surrounds the aluminum stopping target and is designed to detect the signal electron produced by $\mu - e$ neutrinoless conversion. The first component of the CyDet is the Cylindrical Drift Chamber (CDC), which is responsible for tracking the 105 MeV signal electron and measuring its momentum with a resolution better than 200 keV/c [4]. The CDC features approximately 5,000 stereo wires, providing 3D position measurement, and uses a helium-based gas to minimize multiple scattering. Basic performance tests of the CDC have been conducted using cosmic rays. The full readout test and construction of the gas system are currently underway. The second component of the CyDet is the Cylindrical Trigger Hodoscope (CTH). Its primary functions are triggering and timing measurement, but it has also demonstrated excellent performance in e/μ separation [10]. The time resolution is required to be better than 1 ns. The CTH consists of two wheels of plastic scintillators with embedded fibers and Multi-Pixel Photon Counters (MPPCs). The trigger, with a rate required to be less than 100 kHz, is based on four-fold coincidences. Construction of the detector is currently ongoing and the mass production of the front-end electronics will begin shortly.

CRV: Atmospheric muons, produced by cosmic ray interactions in the atmosphere, represent a major source of background events for COMET. A high-momentum atmospheric muon can enter the detector and either produce an electron with energy in the signal region or be misidentified as an electron in the CyDet. To mitigate this background, a dedicated sub-detector has been designed as a veto system for cosmic-ray-induced particles: the Cosmic Ray Veto (CRV). It is box-shaped, surrounding the DS, and features a hybrid design : scintillators where the highest cosmic ray flux is expected, and resistive plate chambers (RPCs) in very high radiation areas. The first scintillator module has been constructed and is currently undergoing commissioning with cosmic rays.

StrECAL: Detectors intended for Phase-II will also be used during Phase-I to carry out a beam measurement program. These detectors consist of Straw Tube Tracker and an Electromagnetic Calorimeter (ECAL), collectively referred to as the StrECAL. The Straw Tube Tracker is designed to track the signal electron and measure its momentum. The required momentum resolution is the same as that of the CDC (200 keV/c). These tracker modules are composed of thin-walled straw tube gas detectors [5]. The first station of straws was already commissioned during Phase- α , while the other stations are currently under construction. The ECAL, on the other hand, is designed to measure the energy, position, and timing of the signal electron. The required energy resolution is below 5% at the expected signal energy (~ 105 MeV). The ECAL is composed of high-density LYSO crystal scintillators. A prototype, consisting of an 8×8 crystal array, demonstrated an energy resolution of 3.9%—better than the requirement—with a timing resolution of approximately 0.5 ns. Construction of the detector is currently ongoing.

5 Conclusion

COMET Phase-I will search for neutrinoless muon to electron conversion with a target sensitivity which is a factor of 100 better than the current limit. The Phase-I is expected to start with low intensity ($\sim 10\%$ power) runs in 2027 for commissioning the detector and the muon beam line, before reaching the nominal beam intensity. In addition to the physics measurement, COMET Phase-I will fully characterise the muon beam and the backgrounds with the detectors of Phase-II. A sensitivity of $O(10^{-17})$ is expected to be reached by COMET Phase-II thanks to improved muon beam intensity, together with backgrounds and systematics under control.

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